

Refugee-Led Organizations and Integration Outcomes among Burmese Refugees in Malaysia: Evidence on Social Cohesion, Long-Term Aspirations, and Psychosocial Well-Being

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ABSTRACT

In Malaysia's restrictive protection environment, Burmese refugees face severely constrained access to formal healthcare, education, and livelihood opportunities, increasing reliance on refugee-led organizations (RLOs) for community-based support. This cross-sectional survey (N = 103) examined whether RLO service receipt is associated with social cohesion, long-term aspirations, and psychosocial well-being; identified which service categories best predict social cohesion; and assessed whether family presence is associated with integration-relevant outcomes; supplementary analysis also explored whether outcomes varied by length of stay. RLO services received were positively associated with social cohesion ($r = .62, p < .001$), long-term aspirations ($r = .55, p < .001$), and psychosocial well-being ($r = .60, p < .001$). A service-specific regression model was statistically significant, $F(6, 96) = 18.59, p < .001$, explaining substantial variance in social cohesion ($R^2 = .54$, adjusted $R^2 = .51$), with health/medical assistance emerging as the strongest positive predictor ($B = .40, p = .001$), followed by skills training ($B = .24, p = .004$) and mental health support ($B = .23, p = .020$). Notably, guidance related to UNHCR processes was negatively associated with social cohesion ($B = -0.34, p < .001$), suggesting that individuals accessing administrative services may represent a subgroup experiencing heightened precarity. Family presence was significantly associated with higher long-term aspirations ($p = .01$) and psychosocial well-being ($p = .02$). Supplementary analysis revealed that refugees residing in Malaysia for 2–5 years reported lower aspirations and psychosocial well-being than recently arrived refugees, indicating a mid-term vulnerability phase in protracted displacement. These findings indicate that RLO service receipt is closely associated with integration-relevant outcomes including future orientation and psychosocial functioning in a legally constrained context, highlighting the importance of community-led health, psychosocial, and skills-based programming, particularly for refugees in the mid-term phase of displacement.

Keywords: *refugee-led organizations; Burmese refugees; Malaysia; social cohesion; psychosocial well-being*

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century is marked by unprecedented levels of forced displacement, intensifying the challenge of refugee inclusion in host societies. Refugees commonly face structural constraints that limit access to lawful employment, education, and healthcare, alongside psychosocial stressors linked to uncertainty and protracted displacement. In this context, refugee-led organizations (RLOs) initiatives designed and governed by refugees have increasingly been recognized as critical community-based actors that provide practical assistance, build social connections, and strengthen community agency (Betts et al., 2021; Harley, 2023; Pincock et al., 2021).

Recent global figures underscore the scale and urgency of this issue. By mid-2024, the number of forcibly displaced people worldwide reached 122.6 million, including 43.7 million refugees (UNHCR, 2024). Southeast Asia hosts substantial displaced populations, and Malaysia remains a key destination for refugees from Myanmar. UNHCR registration data indicate that, as of end October 2025, Malaysia hosted over 211,000 registered refugees and asylum-seekers, the majority originating from Myanmar (UNHCR Malaysia, 2025). However, Malaysia is not a State Party to the 1951 Refugee Convention, and refugees' access to formal systems of protection and basic services is consequently constrained, heightening reliance on community-driven support (UNHCR Malaysia, 2025).

Against this backdrop, RLOs may be especially important for sustaining well-being and integration-related outcomes. Evidence suggests that refugee-led initiatives often respond rapidly to community needs and can deliver services that formal structures do not reach particularly in health and psychosocial support while also advancing self-reliance and collective agency (Betts et al., 2021; Pincock et al., 2021). Yet, despite growing attention to RLOs, less is known about how specific categories of RLO services relate to measurable integration outcomes such as social cohesion, long-term aspirations, and psychosocial well-being in protracted, legally constrained settings. Given that Malaysia hosts a predominantly long-staying refugee population, this study also examines whether integration-relevant outcomes vary by length of stay, recognising that protracted displacement without legal recognition may produce distinct phases of vulnerability over time. This study addresses that gap by examining Burmese refugees in Malaysia and assessing how RLO service receipt and specific service categories relate to key integration outcomes.

Problem Statement and Research Gap

Despite growing recognition that refugee-led organizations (RLOs) are key community-based actors, empirical evidence on their specific contributions to integration-related outcomes remains limited, particularly in restrictive policy environments such as Malaysia. Existing scholarship and programming discussions often emphasize top-down responses led by states and established humanitarian organizations, while refugee-led initiatives shaped by lived experience, community trust, and context-specific knowledge remain comparatively under-measured in quantitative research (Betts et al., 2021; Pincock et al., 2021). In settings characterized by prolonged legal uncertainty and constrained access to formal employment, education, and healthcare, displacement may become a sustained "state of limbo" with implications for psychosocial well-being and future orientation over time (UNHCR, 2024; UNHCR Malaysia, 2025). However, limited research has examined how RLO service receipt relates to measurable outcomes such as social cohesion, long-term aspirations, and psychosocial well-being among Burmese refugees in Malaysia.

Research Questions

RQ-1: Are RLO services received associated with social cohesion (SC), long-term aspirations (LA), and psychosocial well-being (PWB) among Burmese refugees in Malaysia?

RQ-2: Which categories of RLO services are the strongest statistical predictors of social cohesion among Burmese refugees in Malaysia?

RQ-3: Is family presence associated with long-term aspirations and psychosocial well-being among Burmese refugees in Malaysia?

The objectives of this study are:

- (1) to examine associations between RLO services received and social cohesion, long-term aspirations, and psychosocial well-being among Burmese refugees in Malaysia;
- (2) to identify which specific categories of RLO services are the strongest predictors of social cohesion; and
- (3) to assess whether family presence is associated with long-term aspirations and psychosocial well-being among Burmese refugees in Malaysia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Malaysia's Restrictive Protection Context and "Life in Limbo"

Malaysia hosts a substantial refugee and asylum-seeker population but remains outside the formal international refugee protection regime because it is not a State Party to the 1951 Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol. In practice, refugees lack secure legal status and experience constrained access to formal employment, education, and public services conditions that intensify precarity and dependence on informal and community-based support systems (UNHCR, 2024; UNHCR Malaysia, 2025). This policy environment shapes integration as a long-term process of negotiation under uncertainty rather than a linear pathway toward stable incorporation.

Within this context, "limbo" is not only a descriptive label but a structural condition produced by prolonged legal insecurity, restricted rights, and limited access to opportunities. Research on Rohingya refugees in Malaysia highlights how prolonged displacement can normalize insecurity and undermine future planning, even as refugees remain in Malaysia due to relative safety, social ties, and perceived lack of alternatives (Nazri et al., 2024). Such conditions are consistent with the proposition that length of stay may not always produce improved integration outcomes; instead, extended displacement without rights may erode aspirations and psychosocial well-being over time.

2.2 Health Inequities, Exclusion, and Barriers to Well-Being

Access to healthcare in Malaysia is a recurring axis of inequity for refugees and asylum seekers. Narrative review synthesizing evidence on refugees and asylum seekers in Malaysia documents systemic barriers such as unaffordable costs, fear of arrest, and persistent exclusion from public services, with consequences for safety, dignity, and health outcomes (Gopalan et al., 2025). Complementing this synthesis, qualitative research on refugee health in Malaysia shows that barriers to healthcare are shaped by legal status constraints, financial barriers, limited institutional coverage, and practical fears surrounding enforcement and documentation, producing delayed or foregone care and worsening health vulnerabilities (Chuah et al., 2018; Chuah et al., 2019). These structural barriers are important for integration research because they operate not only as health determinants but also as social determinants, influencing belonging, trust, and daily functioning.

The consequences of displacement are also psychological. Refugees commonly face a dual burden of pre-migration trauma exposure and post-migration stressors such as poverty, social exclusion, discrimination, and uncertainty, elevating risks of depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress symptoms (Byrow et al., 2019; Byrow et al., 2020; Silove et al., 2017). Prior work further indicates that post-migration living difficulties and social support are central predictors of psychological adjustment, suggesting that community-based support can operate as a protective factor (Schweitzer et al., 2006). Taken together, the Malaysian context characterized by constrained rights and service access offers a strong rationale for examining how community-led support and service provision relate to psychosocial well-being.

2.3 Refugee-Led Organizations: Definition, Roles, and the “Epistemic Advantage”

Refugee-led organizations (RLOs) have gained increasing attention as community-based actors that organize collective responses to displacement challenges. UNHCR (2023) defines an RLO as an organization or group led primarily by people with lived experience of forced displacement and focused on responding to refugee and related community needs. This definition emphasizes both leadership structure and mission orientation and distinguishes RLOs from externally led service providers.

Scholarly work argues that refugee-led initiatives frequently represent the “first and last responders” in crisis and service gaps, particularly where state protection and formal humanitarian coverage are limited (Betts et al., 2021). In humanitarian governance debates, refugee-led action is also framed as a corrective to top-down aid models: refugee communities often organize effective responses, yet these efforts are frequently undervalued in funding and decision-making structures (Pincock et al., 2021). Empirical analysis of Rohingya community organizations in Malaysia similarly shows that refugee-led groups can become focal points for welfare provision, informal protection, education support, and advocacy, leveraging social capital and local networks to navigate an ambivalent asylum regime (Gopal & Chan, 2022). These findings suggest that RLOs can partially compensate for exclusion from formal institutions and may shape integration outcomes through both service delivery and community cohesion.

A key theoretical justification for studying RLOs is their “epistemic advantage” the idea that lived experience provides context-specific knowledge, trust, and social embeddedness that external actors often lack. Patterns of refugee organizing under protracted displacement illustrate how refugee-led structures emerge to meet needs, build community capacity, and develop legitimacy through relational accountability (El-Abed et al., 2023). In addition to service provision, advocacy-oriented commentary suggests that RLOs may challenge power asymmetries in humanitarian systems by institutionalizing refugee participation and leadership (Ishimwe & Halakhe, 2025). While such perspectives often come from policy-oriented outlets, they align with peer-reviewed arguments on localization and refugee-led governance (Pincock et al., 2021).

2.4 Social Cohesion as an Integration Outcome

Social cohesion is widely conceptualized as a multidimensional construct encompassing trust, belonging, cooperative norms, and the capacity to manage diversity without conflict. A scoping review links social cohesion to social well-being through community assets, trust, and a sense of belonging, while also noting that segregation and exclusionary dynamics can weaken cohesion (Fowler Davis & Davies, 2025). In displacement settings, a major synthesis on forced displacement emphasizes that investments improving service access and reducing inequalities can prevent tension and strengthen cohesion, particularly where competition over resources is politicized (World Bank et al., 2022). This evidence supports the proposition that community-

based service access especially health, education, and livelihood support may function as mechanisms that strengthen cohesion within refugee communities and between refugees and host-society actors.

RLOs may operationalize social cohesion by offering culturally grounded activities that reduce isolation, cultivate mutual trust, and connect community members to practical opportunities. In constrained environments where formal integration mechanisms are limited, the capacity of RLOs to create spaces for cooperation and mutual aid may be especially salient, making social cohesion a plausible outcome of sustained RLO service engagement (Gopal & Chan, 2022; Pincock et al., 2021).

2.5 Long-Term Aspirations under Constrained Mobility and Protracted Displacement

Long-term aspirations among displaced populations are shaped by perceived opportunity structures rather than individual optimism alone. The “capability to aspire” perspective emphasizes that aspirations depend on whether individuals perceive realistic pathways to pursue goals, which are influenced by resources, recognition, and institutional constraints (Consoli, 2024). In displacement and constrained mobility contexts, theorizing highlights that aspirations remain complex and adaptive: refugees may maintain future orientation even under severe restriction, but aspirations can shift depending on legal uncertainty, opportunity access, and social support (Müller-Funk et al., 2023). Evidence from refugee youth also demonstrates that material and relational supports influence aspiration formation and resilience, suggesting that supportive community environments can protect future orientation (El Halaby, 2019).

In Malaysia, extended displacement without legal recognition may weaken perceived pathways to education, work, and stability, thereby reducing long-term aspirations over time (Nazri et al., 2024). Conversely, service access and skill-building opportunities often delivered through community-led structures may strengthen perceived feasibility of future goals and preserve future orientation. This provides a basis for examining how RLO services and length of stay relate to long-term aspirations among Burmese refugees.

2.6 Psychosocial and Mental Well-Being: Stressors, Protection, and Community-Based Support

Refugee mental health is shaped by both trauma exposure and post-migration stressors, and barriers to help-seeking can further compound distress (Byrow et al., 2019; Byrow et al., 2020). Broader reviews underscore that legal insecurity, exclusion, and chronic stress increase risk for mental health difficulties, and that psychosocial supports and social connectedness can function as protective resources (Schweitzer et al., 2006; Silove et al., 2017). In Malaysia, structural constraints and barriers to healthcare access plausibly exacerbate psychological strain, making psychosocial well-being a core integration-related outcome rather than a secondary concern (Chuah et al., 2018; Gopalan et al., 2025).

Building on the theoretical and empirical foundations reviewed above, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H1: RLO services received are positively associated with social cohesion, long-term aspirations, and psychosocial well-being among Burmese refugees in Malaysia.

H2: Health/medical assistance is the strongest positive predictor of social cohesion among RLO service categories.

H3: Family presence is positively associated with long-term aspirations and psychosocial well-being among Burmese refugees in Malaysia.

The literature indicates that Malaysia's restrictive protection environment produces sustained barriers to services and rights, shaping a prolonged "limbo" condition that can undermine well-being and future orientation (Nazri et al., 2024; UNHCR Malaysia, 2025). Concurrently, refugee-led organizations are increasingly recognized as essential community-based actors that deliver services, organize mutual aid, and contribute to refugee governance, potentially strengthening integration outcomes even in the absence of formal protections (Betts et al., 2021; Gopal & Chan, 2022; Pincock et al., 2021). Building on these foundations, the present study examines how RLO services relate to social cohesion, long-term aspirations, and psychosocial well-being among Burmese refugees in Malaysia, and assesses whether outcomes vary by length of stay and family presence factors central to protracted displacement and resilience.

METHODS

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a quantitative cross-sectional survey design to examine associations between RLO engagement (services received) and three integration-related outcomes among Burmese refugees in Malaysia: social cohesion (SC), long-term aspirations (LA), and psychosocial well-being (PWB). A cross-sectional approach was appropriate for estimating relationships among variables at a single time point and for testing the study hypotheses using correlational and regression-based analyses.

3.2 Participants and Sampling

The target population comprised Burmese refugees residing in Malaysia. A non-probability purposive sampling method was employed due to the absence of a complete sampling frame and the practical constraints of accessing refugee populations. Participants were recruited at the Myanmar Ethnic Organization community centre while visiting the facility to receive assistance related to UNHCR processes or other community-based support services. To reduce overrepresentation of any single subgroup and to reflect diversity within the Burmese refugee community, maximum variation purposive sampling was used to recruit participants across different ethnic backgrounds and lived circumstances. It is acknowledged that recruitment at a single community centre introduced a convenience element, which may limit the representativeness of the sample beyond the MEO service context.

A total of 120 questionnaires were distributed, and 103 were completed and returned, yielding a response rate of 85.8%. Among respondents, 62.1% (n = 64) identified as male, 35.0% (n = 36) as female, and 2.9% (n = 3) as other. The largest age group was 18–30 years (52.4%, n = 54), followed by 31–49 years (36.9%, n = 38) and 50 years and above (11.0%, n = 11). Regarding educational attainment, 55.3% (n = 57) reported completing high school, 24.3% (n = 25) reported college education, 13.6% (n = 14) reported secondary education or below, and 6.8% (n = 7) reported a master's degree or higher. Most participants reported residing in Malaysia for five years or more (57.3%, n = 59), followed by 2–5 years (25.2%, n = 26) and one year or less (17.5%, n = 18). Finally, 81.6% (n = 84) reported having family present in Malaysia, while 18.4% (n = 19) reported no family presence. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection.

3.3 Hypotheses

Hypotheses derived from the literature review are tested in the analyses reported below.

3.4 Instrumentation and Measures

Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire with 5-point Likert-type responses (1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*). The instrument measured RLO services received and three outcome constructs: social cohesion (SC), long-term aspirations (LA), and psychosocial well-being (PWB). For each construct, items were averaged to compute composite mean scores, with higher scores indicating higher levels of the construct. Table 1 presents the mean-interpretation rubric used for descriptive reporting; this rubric did not affect inferential analyses.

Table 1
Scoring Systems

Numeric Scale	Scale Average Weight	Scaled Responses	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
3	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Moderate
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

3.5 Reliability

Internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach’s alpha (α). All scales demonstrated satisfactory to excellent reliability: services received (13 items, $\alpha = .915$), SC (7 items, $\alpha = .865$), LA (6 items, $\alpha = .858$), and PWB (6 items, $\alpha = .907$). These values exceeded the commonly used threshold of $\alpha \geq .70$, supporting internal consistency for scale scores used in subsequent analyses.

3.6 Data Collection Procedure and Ethics

Questionnaires were administered at the community centre. Participants were informed of the study purpose, the voluntary nature of participation, and confidentiality protections. Informed consent was obtained prior to participation.

3.7 Data Analysis

Data were analysed using SPSS. Descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, frequencies) were used to summarize participant characteristics and primary variables. Pearson correlation coefficients were computed to examine bivariate associations between study variables. Group differences were assessed using independent-samples t tests for binary grouping variables (e.g., family presence) and one-way ANOVA for multi-group comparisons (e.g., length-of-stay categories). Where omnibus ANOVA tests were significant, appropriate post hoc comparisons were conducted. A multiple linear regression model was estimated to assess which specific categories of RLO services were the strongest predictors of social cohesion, consistent with the study hypotheses. As a supplementary exploratory analysis, a one-way ANOVA was conducted to examine whether social cohesion, long-term aspirations, and psychosocial well-being differed by length of stay.

RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive Overview of Key Study Variables

Participants reported high levels of engagement with Refugee-Led Organizations (RLOs). Mean scores indicated high involvement in RLOs ($M = 4.16$, $SD = 0.60$) and high levels of

services received ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 0.52$; see Table 2). Across outcome variables, respondents reported generally high levels of psychosocial well-being ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.58$), social cohesion ($M = 3.96$, $SD = 0.56$), and long-term aspirations ($M = 3.86$, $SD = 0.58$; see Table 3). Among specific service categories (Table 4), guidance toward UNHCR-related assistance received the highest mean score ($M = 4.23$, $SD = 0.64$), followed by court/legal assistance ($M = 4.16$, $SD = 0.71$) and health/medical assistance ($M = 4.13$, $SD = 0.59$). Mental health support was also rated highly ($M = 4.07$, $SD = 0.59$), while skills training ($M = 3.85$, $SD = 0.66$) and personal development support ($M = 3.84$, $SD = 0.66$) were comparatively lower but remained within the “high” range.

Table 2
RLO Involvement and Services Received

	N	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Level of Refugees’ Involvement in RLOs	103	4.16	0.60	High
Refugee Services Received from RLOs	103	4.04	0.52	High

Table 3
Descriptive Statistics for SC, LA, and PWB

Dependent Variable	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Psychosocial Well-Being	4.00	0.58	High
Social Cohesion	3.96	0.56	High
Long-Term Aspirations	3.86	0.58	High

Table 4
Service Categories Received (Means and Standard Deviations)

RLO Service Category	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Guideline toward UNHCR Assistance	4.23	0.64	Very High
Court and Legal Assistance	4.16	0.71	High
Health and Medical Assistance	4.13	0.59	High
Mental Health Support	4.07	0.59	High
Skills Training (Soft Skills)	3.85	0.66	High
Personal Development Support	3.84	0.66	High

Note. Table presents the six service category composites. The full 13-item scale was used for reliability analysis and all correlation analyses ($\alpha = .915$).

4.2 RQ-1: Are RLO Services Received Associated with SC, LA, and PWB?

Pearson correlation analyses indicated that services received from RLOs were positively associated with all three outcome variables. Specifically, services received showed a moderate-to-strong positive association with social cohesion ($r = .62$, $p < .001$), long-term aspirations ($r = .55$, $p < .001$), and psychosocial well-being ($r = .60$, $p < .001$; see Table 5). These findings

suggest that higher levels of engagement with RLO services are associated with greater social connectedness, stronger future orientation, and better psychosocial functioning.

Hypothesis 1 (H1) was supported. Services received from RLOs were significantly and positively associated with social cohesion, long-term aspirations, and psychosocial well-being.

Table 5

Correlations Between Services Received and SC, LA, and PWB

Variable	Refugee Services Received from RLOs	
Social Cohesion	Pearson r	.617**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	< .001
Long-Term Aspirations	Pearson r	.553**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	< .001
Psychosocial Well-Being	Pearson r	.604**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	< .001

Note. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.3 RQ-2: Which Categories of RLO Services are the Strongest Predictors of Social Cohesion?

A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine whether specific RLO service categories predicted social cohesion. The overall model was statistically significant, $F(6, 96) = 18.59$, $p < .001$, explaining a substantial proportion of variance in social cohesion ($R^2 = .54$, adjusted $R^2 = .51$; see Table 6). Among the predictors, health/medical assistance emerged as the strongest positive predictor of social cohesion ($B = 0.40$, $SE = 0.12$, $\beta = .42$, $p = .001$). Skills training ($B = 0.24$, $SE = 0.08$, $\beta = .29$, $p = .004$) and mental health support ($B = 0.23$, $SE = 0.10$, $\beta = .24$, $p = .020$) were also significant positive predictors. In contrast, guidance toward UNHCR-related assistance was a significant negative predictor of social cohesion ($B = -0.34$, $SE = 0.08$, $\beta = -.40$, $p < .001$). Court/legal assistance ($p = .799$) and personal development support ($p = .207$) were not significant predictors.

Hypothesis 2 (H2) was supported. Health/medical assistance was identified as the strongest positive predictor of social cohesion based on standardized coefficients.

Table 6

Multiple Linear Regression Predicting Social Cohesion from RLO Service Categories

Predictor	B	SE	β	t	p
(Constant)	1.574	0.318		4.945	< .001
Guideline toward UNHCR Assistance	-0.342	0.077	-0.396	-4.423	< .001
Skills Training (Soft Skills)	0.240	0.082	0.285	2.916	.004
Health and Medical Assistance	0.399	0.119	0.423	3.343	.001
Court and Legal Assistance	-0.023	0.089	-0.029	-0.256	.799
Personal Development Support	0.114	0.090	0.135	1.269	.207
Mental Health Support	0.225	0.095	0.239	2.358	.020

Note. $R = .733$, $R^2 = .537$, Adjusted $R^2 = .509$, SE of the Estimate = .390. Dependent variable: Social Cohesion.

4.4 RQ-3: Is Family Presence Associated with Long-Term Aspirations and Psychosocial Well-Being?

Independent-samples t tests were conducted to compare participants with and without family present in Malaysia on long-term aspirations and psychosocial well-being. For long-term aspirations, Levene's test for equality of variances was significant, $F = 28.81$, $p < .001$, indicating that equal variances could not be assumed. Participants with family present reported significantly higher long-term aspirations than those without family present, $t(27.39) = 2.65$, $p = .010$. Similarly, for psychosocial well-being, Levene's test was significant, $F = 9.78$, $p = .003$, and equal variances were not assumed. Participants with family present reported significantly higher psychosocial well-being, $t(40.26) = 2.55$, $p = .020$.

Hypothesis 3 (H3) was supported. Family presence was associated with significantly higher long-term aspirations and psychosocial well-being.

Table 7

Independent Samples t Tests for Family Presence on LA and PWB

Variable	Levene's F	Levene's p	t	df	p (two-sided)	Mean Diff.
Long-Term Aspirations	28.811	< .001	2.22	42	.030	0.37
			2.645	27.393	.010	0.37
Psychosocial Well-Being	9.777	.003	2.302	42	.030	0.37
			2.545	40.259	.020	0.37

Note. Top row per variable = equal variances assumed; bottom row = equal variances not assumed (reported values).

Additional Analysis: Differences in LA and PWB by Length of Stay

One-way ANOVA revealed significant differences by length of stay for long-term aspirations, $F(2, 100) = 3.36$, $p = .039$, and psychosocial well-being, $F(2, 100) = 3.68$, $p = .029$, but not for social cohesion, $F(2, 100) = 2.01$, $p = .139$. Tukey HSD post hoc tests showed that participants residing for one year or less reported significantly higher long-term aspirations and psychosocial well-being than those residing for 2–5 years ($p < .05$), with no other significant group differences. These findings suggest a mid-term decline in aspirations and psychosocial well-being among refugees in the 2–5-year group, with no clear evidence of recovery at longer durations.

Table 8

One-Way ANOVA Results for SC, LA, and PWB by Length of Stay

Variable	Source	SS	df	MS	F	p
Social Cohesion	Between Groups	1.225	2	0.612	2.014	.139
	Within Groups	30.409	100	0.304		
	Total	31.634	102			

Long-Term Aspirations	Between Groups	2.129	2	1.064	3.357	.039
	Within Groups	31.710	100	0.317		
	Total	33.839	102			
Psychosocial Well-Being	Between Groups	2.387	2	1.194	3.675	.029
	Within Groups	32.474	100	0.325		
	Total	34.861	102			

Table 9

Tukey HSD Post Hoc Comparisons for LA and PWB by Length of Stay

Outcome Variable	Group Comparison	Mean Diff. (I–J)	SE	p	95% CI
Long-Term Aspirations	< 1 yr vs. 2–5 yrs	0.366	0.14	0.035*	[0.023, 0.709]
	< 1 yr vs. ≥5 yrs	0.049	0.08	0.817	[–0.145, 0.244]
	2–5 yrs vs. ≥5 yrs	–0.317	0.16	0.114	[–0.693, 0.060]
Psychosocial Well-Being	< 1 yr vs. 2–5 yrs	0.374	0.15	0.039*	[0.016, 0.732]
	< 1 yr vs. ≥5 yrs	0.032	0.11	0.956	[–0.239, 0.303]
	2–5 yrs vs. ≥5 yrs	–0.342	0.15	0.058	[–0.694, 0.010]
Social Cohesion	All comparisons			ns	

Note. * $p < .05$.

DISCUSSION

This study examined the relationship between Refugee-Led Organization (RLO) services and integration-relevant outcomes among Burmese refugees in Malaysia. Four key findings emerge. First, RLO service receipt was positively associated with social cohesion, long-term aspirations, and psychosocial well-being. Second, among service categories, health/medical assistance was the strongest predictor of social cohesion, followed by skills training and mental health support. Third, family presence was associated with higher long-term aspirations and psychosocial well-being. Fourth, supplementary analysis suggested a potential mid-term decline in aspirations and psychosocial well-being among refugees residing in Malaysia for 2–5 years.

RQ1: RLO Services and Integration Outcomes

The positive associations observed between RLO service receipt and all three outcome variables suggest that access to community-based support is closely linked to both psychosocial functioning and broader integration-related capacities. In Malaysia's restrictive protection environment, where refugees have limited access to formal employment, education, and healthcare, RLOs appear to function as critical compensatory mechanisms that mitigate

structural exclusion. These findings are consistent with prior scholarship positioning refugee-led initiatives as essential service providers and community anchors in contexts where formal institutional access is constrained (Betts et al., 2021; Pincock et al., 2021). Importantly, the strength and consistency of the correlations across social cohesion, long-term aspirations, and psychosocial well-being indicate that RLO engagement may extend beyond immediate service provision to support relational and future-oriented dimensions of integration. However, given the cross-sectional design, these associations should not be interpreted as causal. Longitudinal research is required to establish directionality.

RQ2: Service-Specific Predictors of Social Cohesion

The regression results provide further insight into how different types of services relate to social cohesion. Health/medical assistance emerged as the strongest positive predictor, with additional contributions from skills training and mental health support. This pattern aligns with theoretical and empirical work suggesting that access to essential services reduces vulnerability, enhances perceived stability, and enables participation in social life (World Bank et al., 2022). Health services may play a foundational role by addressing immediate physical vulnerabilities that otherwise constrain social engagement. Skills training may contribute through the development of self-efficacy and opportunities for structured interaction, while mental health support may reduce psychological barriers to participation and trust-building.

The negative association observed for guidance related to UNHCR processes warrants careful interpretation. Rather than indicating a detrimental effect of the service itself, this finding likely reflects underlying differences in the population accessing such services. Individuals seeking administrative or legal guidance may be experiencing heightened uncertainty, legal insecurity, or crisis conditions, which may independently correspond with lower perceived social cohesion. This interpretation is consistent with prior research indicating that refugee-led services often disproportionately serve individuals facing acute precarity (Pincock et al., 2021).

RQ3: Family Presence and Well-Being

Family presence was significantly associated with higher long-term aspirations and psychosocial well-being, reinforcing the well-established role of social support in promoting psychological resilience among displaced populations (Schweitzer et al., 2006). In contexts of protracted displacement, family networks may provide both emotional stability and practical support, sustaining hope and future-oriented thinking under conditions of uncertainty.

Additional Analysis: Length of Stay and Mid-Term Decline

Supplementary analysis indicated that refugees residing in Malaysia for 2–5 years reported significantly lower long-term aspirations and psychosocial well-being compared to newly arrived individuals. This pattern suggests the possibility of a mid-term vulnerability phase in protracted displacement, during which initial resilience may erode as structural barriers persist and opportunities remain limited. However, these findings should be interpreted with caution. Length of stay was not a primary research objective, and differences between the 2–5-year group and those residing for five years or more were not statistically significant. Future research incorporating longitudinal designs and explicit hypotheses is needed to determine whether this mid-term decline represents a consistent trajectory.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that, within a context of restricted formal protection, engagement with Refugee-Led Organization (RLO) services is systematically associated with higher social cohesion, stronger long-term aspirations, and better psychosocial well-being among Burmese refugees in Malaysia. These findings underscore the role of RLOs not only as service providers but also as key social infrastructures supporting integration-relevant capacities under conditions of institutional constraint.

Service-specific findings further refine this contribution. Health/medical assistance emerged as the strongest predictor of social cohesion, with additional positive contributions from skills training and mental health support. These results suggest that addressing immediate vulnerabilities and enabling participation are central pathways through which social cohesion is strengthened. At the same time, the negative association observed for UNHCR-related guidance likely reflects underlying vulnerability among service users rather than a substantive negative effect of the service itself. Exploratory findings suggest a possible mid-term vulnerability phase among refugees residing for 2–5 years; however, this requires confirmation in future longitudinal research before firm conclusions can be drawn.

Implications for Policy and Practice

The findings carry several implications for policy and programming. First, the consistent associations between RLO service receipt and integration outcomes suggest that strengthening RLO capacity should be treated as a central intervention strategy rather than a peripheral one. Second, investment in health/medical and mental health services may yield both individual and community-level benefits by reducing vulnerability and enabling participation. Third, skills training programmes should be designed not only for economic outcomes but also as platforms for social interaction and cohesion-building. Fourth, individuals accessing UNHCR-related guidance may represent a particularly vulnerable subgroup, highlighting the need for integrated service models that combine administrative support with psychosocial assistance. Finally, the potential mid-term decline in well-being and aspirations suggests that support strategies should extend beyond newly arrived refugees to include those in the intermediate phase of displacement.

Limitations and Directions for Future Research

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference, and the observed relationships should be interpreted as correlational. Second, the use of a single recruitment site limits generalisability beyond the specific RLO context studied. Third, as all participants were already engaged with RLO services, the study does not capture outcomes among refugees who are not accessing such services, limiting comparative inference. Future research should adopt longitudinal and mixed-method designs to examine how integration outcomes evolve over time and to better establish causal pathways. Expanding data collection across multiple RLOs and including comparison groups would further strengthen the evidence base.

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